

INFLUENCE OF ULTRASONIC ODONTOPREPARATION ON THE MORPHOLOGY OF DENTAL HARD TISSUES

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Annotation: From a comparative perspective, the results of ultrasonic and morphological studies of classical dental hard tissues are presented. Significant morphological differences are identified in dental micropreparations. The fact is that ultrasound is a gentle method for preparing teeth.

Keywords: tooth preparation, ultrasonic method, baby, tooth shape

Introduction: Odontopreparation is an action on the hard tissues of the tooth to remove pathologically altered tissues and maintain the strength properties of the tooth, creating a cavity shape that provides a comfortable and technical filling that maintains the seal strength, reliable fixation, aesthetics and medical efficiency. Properly implemented cavity preparation eliminates the possibility of further destruction of hard tissues and ensures a reliable seal of the seal. The basic principle of cavity preparation is the removal of pathologically altered tissues and their gentle reaction to healthy tissue . Restoration and maintenance of the anatomical position of the tooth largely depends on the quality of tooth preparation. In the treatment of caries, dentists use various methods of tooth preparation: traditional, classical – the use of rotary and alternative instruments, innovative – laser, ultrasonic and air-friction. Traditional preparation of hard dental tissues often results in thermal and mechanical irritation, which leads to the destruction of the enamel contour, cracking and necrosis of the tooth enamel, forming a “wounded” dentin surface . Open dentin cracks and canals are weak points of hard dental tissues and can serve as a route for easy penetration of microorganisms . Alternative methods of odontopreparat

minimize such negative effects. Odontopreparat has specificity in pediatric dentistry. The main criteria for choosing a method of preparation of solid dental tissues in children include not only the quality and speed of treatment of caries, but also the painlessness of the operation, which reduces the stress of the child during dental intervention. At the same time, the surfaces of the hard tissues after mechanical processing and the fillers of the preparation must have retentive properties for optimal adhesion. Since traditional preparation methods often cause negative thoughts from children, it is important to practice pediatric dentistry with alternative methods, which mainly involve ultrasonic tooth preparation. The aim of the study was to study the morphological features of the hard tissues of teeth subjected to ultrasound and the relative preparation methods of classical teeth. Morphological examination materials and methods are performed on permanent permanent teeth, which are constantly removed as indicated by orthodontics. Before the start of the study, the teeth were cleaned and separated using ultrasonic or classical methods. Square spaces I of the removed teeth are performed to a depth of 4-5 mm according to the classification of black. The examined dental specimens are divided into two groups, depending on the method of dental preparation used. First group: teeth are prepared using the traditional method. Cavities are made at 300,000 rpm, using forced water-air cooling and diamond spherical holes (Nti) with blue markers (Nti): teeth are prepared by ultrasound. Dental Odontopreparation is carried out with a special diamond-coated drilling nozzle (satlake) with a minimum vibration frequency of 28-36 kHz, which is produced by an ultrasonic generator (satlake-based P5 neutron Xs) based on the effect of reverse piezoelectricity. Preparation is provided by a constant supply of distilled water. Tooth preparations are prepared according to the following method: The test material is placed in a 10-15% formula solution and allowed to set for 4 weeks. Next, dehydration of the teeth is carried out for 10 days in a solution of 6% nitric acid, then neutralized in a 5% aluminum-potassium alum solution during the day. Dehydration of the composition

is carried out in alcohol, the concentration of which is gradually increased from 70% to 96%. The preparation is treated with chloroform and poured into a paraffin block 6 hours after absorbing the paraffin. The paraffin block is prepared for cutting the tooth on a microtome and creating a microformula with a thickness of 7 microns. A total of 6 consecutive sections of the lateral molar crowns were studied. For staining, an aqueous solution of hematoxylin and a solution of eosin alcohol were used. Microscopic and microscopic preparations were studied using the results of the program and the results of the morphological study of the first group of microscopic preparations of teeth treated with classical preparations. The prototype crowns are devoid of enamel. The dentin channels are thin, external, penetrating into the dentin from its surrounding pulp chambers, with an s-shaped and curved orientation, especially in the area adjacent to the enamel contour. The last branches of the dentin canals are observed. The predentin layer is represented by a basophilic area adjacent to the peripheral layer of the pulp, where calcified basophilic particles are introduced into the predentin by adult dentin, a space formed by microbial colonies on the lateral side of the occlusal surface. Morphological image of the solid tissue of the crown in the area of the prepared area. The bottom and walls of the prepared cavity are covered with small grooves cut by transparent teeth. No smooth areas can be observed. The cone of the tooth is about 60 degrees, and the maximum height of the tooth is 2.2 microns. In a lubricating layer in the form of a basophilic wire without microstructure is detected under the cavity and wall area. The results of the morphological study of group 2 of microscopic preparations of teeth are processed with ultrasonic preparations. The prototype of the crown is devoid of enamel. The dentin channels, especially in the area adjacent to the enamel contour, have an s-shaped and curved orientation, are thin outer dentin channels penetrating into the dentin from its surrounding pulp chambers. The last branches of the dentin canals are observed. The predentine layer is represented by a basophilic area adjacent to the marginal layer of the pulp, mineralized basophilic particles are

introduced into the predentine by adult dentin, the occlusion is the surface-side space in which the crown is prepared, which in turn is formed by a colony of microorganisms. Morphological images of tooth micropreparations treated with ultrasonic preparations on the areas of the drug. The bottom and walls of the prepared cavities have small dental denticles, covered with small grooves, variable denticles and smooth tooth areas. The top of the tooth is smooth, with a cone of about 80 degrees, the maximum height of the tooth does not exceed 1.2 microns. Under the gap and in the wall area, the lubricating layer is observed as a thin structureless basophilic line. The lubricating layer is less pronounced in cavities prepared with a rotary device.

To conclude: Thus, the study shows significant morphological differences in the hard tissues of teeth treated with ultrasonics and in the classical method of tooth preparation. The comparative morphological and morphological characteristics show that the severity of the crushed layer is less, the surface of the dentin is more uniform, the upper part of the dentin and the smooth constriction and the maximum height of the dentin in the microscopic preparation of the tooth are relatively treated with the preparation, and the optimal method of preparing the tooth is ultrasonic, which not only provides a painless preparation, but also reduces the stress of the child during dental intervention.

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